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Communication perspectives on social change towards electrification for 2-wheeled vehicle users

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Abstract

This study discusses the perspective of social change communication on electrification for people who use 2-wheeled vehicles. The method used in this study is descriptive qualitative with data collected from journals, articles, and books related to the perspective of social change communication related to electrification for people who use 2-wheeled vehicles which are described empirically. The conclusion obtained is that the public needs to be educated by means of good communication, as a form of the world's green campaign to welcome carbon neutrality in 2030, in this case 2-wheeled electric vehicles can be used as the right and comprehensive mobility solution for users who are currently still using fossil fuel vehicles. This can also be used as part of the social change of society in the current era to reduce the effects of global warming, and reduce the impact of greenhouse gases, especially in urban areas, especially those derived from exhaust gas expenditures in the form of carbon emissions containing pollutants. This change in the use of 2-wheeled electric vehicles also helps in the formation of social changes for the community and the environment to benefit from environmental conditions and healthier air quality.

Keywords: Communication perspective; Social change; 2-Wheeled electric vehicle

1. Introduction

When looking at certain phenomena, especially those that are being studied or observed, perspective as a point of view is very helpful. In addition, the word perspective as a noun can be defined also in several ways depending on the context in which it is used (Hughes, 2005). With the use of perspective, it allows for differences in theories used in interpreting and analyzing a phenomenon. Therefore, it is not surprising that various theories based on existing perspectives are applied to a phenomenon. Perspectives can be used to observe the behavior of people, which will vary depending on the perspective from which they are observed. Likewise, as part of the use of perspectives, the public needs to be educated with good communication, as a form of the world's green campaign to welcome carbon neutrality, in this case 2-wheeled electric vehicles can be used as a mobility solution for 2-wheeled vehicle users who currently still use fossil fuels. It can also be used as part of the social change of society in the current era to reduce the effects of global warming of greenhouse gases in urban areas derived from emissions of carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxides, carbon monoxide and hydrocarbons. This change in the use of 2-wheeled electric vehicles helps in forming social changes, social behavior, and also the formation of a healthier society and environment.

In this case, it can be seen that in communication, perspective is needed to study and research. It is this reason that it is impossible to see such extensive communication from one point of view. While, as Habermas explained,

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communicative action refers to the interaction of two or more subjects in speaking (Fitriyah, Sarwoprasodjo, Sjaf, & Soetarto, 2019). If considering persuasion and propaganda as early theories that marked the emergence of the discipline of communication, this communication perspective is itself a concept influenced by the perspective of other disciplines, such as the perspective of the disciplines of political science and psychology. This perspective plays a very important role in the development of communication science.

Meanwhile, social changes in community institutions that have an impact on the social system of values, attitudes, and behavior patterns are referred to as social change. Social change is progressing at a high pace and also moreover can surpass technological change (Kavanagh, Lightfoot, & Lilley, 2021). This is a substantial change of the social structure through time (Vadrot, 2020). This is related to the fact that social dynamics and shifts will occur in a society. This is what happens when people and groups interact. Especially in this day and age, when new influences have been introduced by technological advances. the emergence of common goals, as well as individual choices and desires, external influences, and social change.

This social change that is happening in society, especially in Indonesia, is now due to advances in vehicle production which are also shifting to keep up with the times. What is being discussed in the community is the acceptance of two-wheeled electric vehicles. It is recorded that based on a recent study in 2020, Indonesia and neighboring countries in Asia experienced enthusiasm for electric vehicle ownership (NISSAN, 2020). This happens because people have begun to realize the importance of creating a more sustainable future. Educational communication can be one of the alternative options to introduce an idea of change, especially in bringing changes to people's behavior so that they are more open and can accept ideas / programs that will be carried out that lead to success in society (Muldi, Damanhuri, & Putri, 2021). Thus, this study was conducted to describe the acceptance of two-wheeled electric vehicles with social changes that occurred.

2. Methods

The approach used in this study is descriptive qualitative. Data is collected by conducting a review of pre-existing research libraries. The data sources are journals, articles, and books related to the perspective of social change communication on electrification for people who use 2-wheeled vehicles. The data found are then described in a series of words and sentences that will be analyzed to show a communication perspective on social changes related to electrification for 2-wheeled vehicles in society.

3. Results and Discussion

In today's era, with science and technology that has become increasingly advanced, it is undeniable that there will also be progress in communication and information technology which has mastered all lines of people's lives. This is seen in everyday life, especially considering that communication technology has managed to consider the entire potential of human and natural resources. The social, cultural, and various other fields have all undergone significant shifts as a result of this dimension. In social change, communication is needed to be able to develop society in a better direction. Communication itself can be seen as the process of conveying information that has certain goals in an organization that has activities or programs that have been arranged in a work plan framework (Fitriyah, 2013).

All members of society, as well as all aspects of culture and social systems, are undergoing social changes, it is possible to imagine. External factors that leave traces of previous life patterns, cultural norms, and social systems affect people from all walks of life during this process. Then it can adapt to a new way of life, culture, and social structure. The new way of thinking adopted by society as a modern attitude has been evenly distributed as a result of the shift in people's mindsets and attitudes towards various social and cultural issues in their immediate environment. In addition, the issue of shifting social systems, in which individuals defect from one system to lead another, is related to behavioral shifts. The change in material culture also means that people's cultural models of clothing, technology, and home appliances—among many others—are changing. These models may change over time to meet the needs of society and time.

The ideas and messages shared by communicators and communicants must undergo a process of mutual adjustment as part of the process of social change. As a result, policymakers provide information, ideas, and thoughts that truly understand not only what is being said. but also the culture of the recipient of the policy or provisions to be enforced. Therefore, communication is important to help explain perspectives or points of view during social change, that is, to inform the general public about the importance of change and provide opportunities for society to actively participate.

4. Acceptance of the Use of Electric Vehicles

The use of vehicles fueled by gasoline has inevitably caused higher pollution. High air pollution causes air quality to become less and less good and can lead to unhealthy communities. This can be a dangerous and precarious environmental problem. In Indonesia, Jakarta is one of the cities with the highest pollution levels in the world on an equal footing with Dubai, Johannesburg, Beijing, and Santiago. The government has gradually continued to encourage people to continue riding electric vehicles in an effort to reduce air pollution. The second initiative, aimed at public transport, is the first time the use of electric vehicles has been initiated by the government.

Online *transportation* applicatives are encouraged to use electric vehicles and the next is that DAMRI will also soon launch the use of electric buses. In addition, the Indonesian people also have a high interest even though they are still skeptical of product capabilities, infrastructure availability, and selling prices (Pratama, 2018). There are currently about 10,300 two-wheeled electric vehicles circulating in the community. However, the government hopes that people will use electric vehicles more often following the issuance of Presidential Regulation 55 of 2019 concerning the Acceleration of the Battery-Based Electric Motor Vehicle Program. Public acceptance of the use of electric vehicles can be seen from the increasing number of ownership of electric motorized vehicles, which initially there were 5 ATPM (Sole Agent of Brand Holders) now there are 22 ATPM of electric motorcycles. The population of electric vehicles has not increased due to the limited availability of public electric vehicle charging stations (SPKLU). Meanwhile, currently, those who are encouraged to use electric vehicles are people who are in urban areas first, so that the provision of supporting infrastructure is also only limited to urban areas and city districts, such as in Dealers or Authorized Workshops, Gas Stations, PLN Service Offices, Malls, Office Complexes and others.

The acceptance of the procurement and use of electric vehicles that are quite good from the community helps the government in creating future transportation which must be an option so that the city's air can remain clean and also environmentally friendly. Even so, the challenge related to electric vehicles is that the price is still quite high, especially in the battery components. Therefore, this battery needs to be tried to be cheaper and easier to obtain. With changes like this, the shift in the use of fossil fuel vehicles to electric vehicles continues to be promoted by the government along with the opening of battery factories and also the intensification of the use of electric vehicles in office environments, so that people will feel called to immediately prepare to be ready to switch to electric vehicles.

4.1. Electric Vehicles: Social Change

With clear communication, social change can be realized. In the campaign to use electric vehicles, clear communication is needed so that the public can understand the importance of using electric vehicles in today's era. Starting from the fact that fossil fuel vehicles such as gasoline and diesel fuel account for 70% of pollution in big cities, such as Jakarta. As previously explained, this makes the city's air quality worse and is part of the contribution to global warming and climate change. Electricity then became an alternative as a vehicle fuel.

By using electricity as vehicle fuel, there will be no residual gas from motor vehicles that always manage to pollute the air and the environment and always threaten public health. Fuel comes from electricity so that it can help in creating a pollution-friendly environment and can be part of sustainable development. This is a development that meets current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to be able to meet their own needs (Kuhlman & Farrington, 2010).

The use of electric vehicles is not only about changing the type of vehicle or the type of vehicle fuel. This is a greater effort to create and produce more advanced social change and also prioritize environmental sustainability and a healthier life. It can be seen that society is in a state of constant equilibrium in which when changes occur in one part of society, adjustments are made, and social changes occur when the balance is compromised due to the speed of events that occur (de la Sablonniere, 2017). It is a dynamic of social change that ushers in a cultural change that can then become a change in habits. Starting with the change in the use of vehicles from fossil fuels to electric vehicles will be able to produce changes in social behavior that can later play a role in sustainable efforts whose impact can be felt, not only by the current generation, but also for future generations.

5. Conclusion

It can be concluded in this study that two-wheeled electric vehicles are an important solution in today's era where pollution has begun to threaten public health and is also dangerous for the sustainability of people's lives. The move or conversion from fossil fuel motor vehicles to two-wheeled electric vehicles is a social change as well as a change in culture and behavior. This is an effort to form a healthier and also more environmentally friendly society so that

sustainable development can be achieved so that it can be enjoyed continuously. Therefore, a good and appropriate communication perspective is needed to facilitate the process of understanding the public regarding two-wheeled electric vehicles. Moreover, communication must be naturally established between the two parties, namely from the government to the community. That way, it is not surprising that public interest in the use of two-wheeled vehicles has begun to increase, although it is still limited to urban areas.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

Authors of this study consist of three different scholars with various backgrounds in which they reside in a similar education institution of Faculty of Social & Political Sciences of University of Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa.

References

- [1] de la Sablonniere, R. (2017). Toward a Psychology of Social Change: A Typology of Social Change. *Front Psychol., Vol. 8 (397)*, DOI: 10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00397.
- [2] Fitriyah, N. (2013). Strategi Komunikasi Pengurus Komisi Penanggulangan AIDS (KPA) Dalam Penanggulangan Epidemi HIV/AIDS di Provinsi Banten. *InterAct, Vol. 2 (1)*, 32-43. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.36388%2Fia.v2i1.739>.
- [3] Fitriyah, N., Sarwoprasodjo, S., Sjaf, S., & Soetarto, E. (2019). Interaksi Politik Jawara dalam Pembangunan Perspektif Tindakan. *Warta ISKI, Vol. 02 (02)*, 104-116. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.25008/wartaiski.v2i02.40>.
- [4] Hughes, I. A. (2005). A perspective on perspectives. *Archives of Disease in Childhood, Vol. 90 (8)*, DOI: 10.1136/adc.2005.073536.
- [5] Kavanagh, D., Lightfoot, G., & Lilley, S. (2021). Are we living in a time of particularly rapid social change? And how might we know? *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120856>.
- [6] Kuhlman, T., & Farrington, J. (2010). What is Sustainability? *Sustainability, Vol. 2*, 3436-3448; doi:10.3390/su2113436.
- [7] Muldi, A., Damanhuri, & Putri, A. (2021). Komunikasi Edukasi untuk Pencegahan Penularan Covid-19 dan Peningkatan Derajat Kesehatan Masyarakat di Kabupaten Serang Banten. *Menara Riau: Jurnal Ilmu Pengetahuan dan Pengembangan Masyarakat Islam, 15(1)*, 43 – 54.
- [8] NISSAN. (2020, Februari 4). *Studi Menunjukkan Antusiasme Terhadap Kendaraan Listrik: Pengendara di Indonesia Siap Menuju ke Listrik*. Retrieved from Nissan FUTURES: <https://nissan.co.id/new-press/artikel/studi-menunjukkan-antusiasme-indonesia-terhadap-kendaraan-listrik/>
- [9] Pratama, R. (2018, Oktober 5). *Kendaraan Listrik di Mata Masyarakat Indonesia*. Retrieved from detikOto: <https://oto.detik.com/mobil/d-4243167/kendaraan-listrik-di-mata-masyarakat-indonesia>
- [10] Vadrot, A. B. (2020). Re-thinking the conditions for social change and innovation. *Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research, Vol. 33 (1)*, 1-3. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13511610.2020.1713455>.